

Seed storage in the nursery (Prunus, Alnus and Pinus spp.)

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Summary

A storage experiment by the Forestry Research Project (FRP) in cooperation with the National Tree Seed Project (NTSP), confirms that the viability of 'orthodox' seed can be maintained significantly longer if the seed is dried adequately and kept dry. Three storage methods were examined, two that are practical for small, remote nurseries, and one (as a control) for a cold store. The species tested were those most commonly used for reforestation in the middle hills of Nepal: Prunus cerasoides, Alnus nepalensis, Pinus roxburghii and Pinus wallichiana.

Introduction

Seed collection and nursery sowing times are often different, so that seed must be stored for a few weeks or months. If it is necessary to insure against poor seed years, more than a year's storage may be needed. Wherever the seed is stored, at the panchayat nursery, district forest office, or central store of the NTSP, it must be stored properly, otherwise it will lose viability and vigour (some species quicker than others), and the labour and expense of collecting it will be wasted. Furthermore, the nurseryman will not be able to meet his seedling production targets.

Seed is usually classified into two storage types (Willan 1985):

- 'orthodox', e.g. Alnus, Pinus and Prunus spp., which can be dried to a low moisture content (5-10 %) and successfully stored for long periods, especially when kept at low temperatures (usually down to 4-5°C).

- 'recalcitrant', e.g. Artocarpus lakoocha, Litsea monopetala and Quercus spp. which cannot survive drying below a relatively high

moisture content (20-50 %), and which cannot be stored for long periods.

While the objective for these two types of seed is the same - to prolong seed viability - the means are very different. The viability of orthodox seed is prolonged by minimizing the respiration of the seed (without otherwise damaging it). Recalcitrant seed must be stored under conditions which permit respiration and which also reduce the deterioration of the seed by promoting good aeration and reducing the temperature.

The most important factors that affect the rate of respiration of orthodox seed stored in the nursery are:

- moisture content,
- temperature,
- atmosphere in the container.

All these factors can be controlled to some extent by the naike, even in small remote nurseries, and fortunately the most important factor - seed moisture content - is the one over which he has most control.

Orthodox seed is dried by placing it in the sun for one to several days (depending on the climate) in raised trays with wire mesh bottoms, so that there is good air circulation, and the moisture can be carried away. It must then be put immediately into thick polythene bags which are tightly sealed with string or wire. Glass jars or locally available plastic containers may also be used, provided they can be sealed tightly.

Under nursery conditions, temperature can be kept to a minimum by placing the seed in the coolest possible place in the store (just off the floor, in a dry, well ventilated place that does not receive the sun). Air (and therefore available oxygen) can be reduced by filling rigid containers full or squeezing polythene bags tightly before sealing.

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Another very important factor must be considered: protection against rodents. Normally, it is best to place the sealed bags in a can or metal trunk. If this is not done rodents are likely to eat through plastic containers and get at the seed. This is a particular problem with pines.

Experiments

Three methods were tested on four commonly planted species: Prunus cerasoides, Alnus nepalensis, Pinus roxburghii and Pinus wallichiana.

1. In a sealed glass jar, in a refrigerator (4-5°C) at the FRP office. This represented storage under ideal conditions similar to those at the NTSP central seed store in Hattisar.

2. In tightly tied thick polythene bags in a metal trunk (see photograph) at Chalnakhel nursery, Kathmandu valley. The seed was kept dry, but the temperature was not controlled.

3. In cloth bags, in the same trunk. There was no control of moisture content, since the seed could absorb moisture through the cloth bag.

The trunk was placed in a cool place in a shed, so that the seed in methods 2 and 3 followed typical good indoor conditions of temperature and (in method 3) relative humidity.

The seed used was taken from source-identified seed lots collected in 1985. It was dried immediately after collection and stored under dry and cold conditions until the start of the experiment in June 1985. Each lot was then tested for germination and moisture content at the NTSP seed testing laboratory, divided into three equal amounts, and packed by the methods described above.

Samples were taken every three months, and tested for germination and moisture content. Six such tests have been carried out so far, covering 15 months, and the experiment will continue for at least another 9 months.

Results and conclusions

The results are shown in the Appendix in tables and graphs. They indicate very clearly - for all species - that the best method is No.1; No.2 is

second best and No.3 is the poorest. The difference between methods 2 and 3 corresponds with the difference in their ability to keep the moisture content low. In all species, seed stored in cloth bags increased in moisture content, particularly during the monsoon season, when the relative humidity was high (after 3-6 months and 12-15 months). There is little difference in the ability of the polythene bags and glass jars to keep the seed dry, although some difference may be seen over a longer period. With regard to temperature, the improvement from keeping the seeds as cool as possible can be clearly seen by comparing methods 1 and 2, where one can assume that the difference is not due to the different containers used.

Some comments on individual species are:

Prunus cerasoides: From an initial germination of 74 % this species lost almost all viability within 3 months when stored under method 3, associated with an increase in moisture content from 9.5 to 12.4 %. With methods 1 and 2 the germination percentages stayed high for the first 9 months, and unexpectedly showed an increase after 3 months to more than 90%. This may be due to after-ripening of the seed, in which dormancy factors were removed. After 9 months, seed stored under method 2 quickly lost viability and germination had fallen to zero by 15 months. Since the moisture content remained almost the same in methods 1 and 2, this decline must be attributed to the much higher temperature in the nursery. Note, however, that temperature did not have any noticeable effect in the first 9 months of storage.

Alnus nepalensis: In a similar manner to Prunus cerasoides, this species lost viability rapidly (from an initial 616 germinants per g) when stored under method 3, and was completely dead within 3 months. Again, this must be attributed to a rise in moisture content, from 10.4 % to 11.8 % (and also to the higher temperature as compared with method 1). Temperature appears to be more critical for Alnus than for Prunus, since under method 2 there was a gradual decline in viability from the beginning of the storage period until 15 months, when all seed was dead. Since the moisture content remained practically the same in methods 1 and 2, this decline must be due to temperature.

Pinus roxburghii: This species shows very different results to the two preceding species, and appears to be much more tolerant of moisture and temperature conditions. Although moisture content increased to 10 % from an initial 8 % with method 3, there was no significant decline in viability for any of the storage methods during the first 12 months. A decline appears to have started at 15 months for both seed lots stored in the nursery, but none is apparent under refrigerated storage.

Pinus wallichiana: This species is much more sensitive than Pinus roxburghii to storage conditions. With method 3 a decline in viability (which accelerated after 6 months) was apparent, and before 15 months all viability was lost. This appears to have been mainly because of the increase in moisture content from 10 % to a maximum of 12.4 %. For the other methods, after-ripening appears to have occurred in the first 6 months - viability increasing to 60 % from an initial 54 %. After that the initial viability of seed stored under method 1 has been maintained, whereas method 2 has shown a decline to 29 % and will probably have lost all viability after 18 months, because of the higher temperature.

Recommendations

The results show that care must be taken to ensure that the seed of orthodox species is adequately dried and kept dry. Details of appropriate techniques will not be discussed here, since they are covered in the NTSP/CFDP Manual of Seed Handling (Robbins and Shrestha, 1986). However, a few general points will be made along with some specific points concerning each species.

An increase of only a few percent in moisture content can cause viability to be lost entirely in a few months. A useful general rule proposed by Harrington (cited by Willan, 1985) suggests that the life of orthodox seed is doubled for every decrease of one percentage point, when it has a moisture content between 5 and 14 %. With Alnus in our experiments, the difference of 1.5 % between cloth and sealed storage would adequately explain the rapid loss in viability. A second general rule proposed by Harrington states that in the range 0-44° C, every decrease of 5 C doubles the

life of orthodox seed. This tendency can be seen in the results of the experiment, but it is apparent that temperature is not as important as moisture content in the early stages.

The following points can be made about individual species:

Prunus cerasoides: This species matures between March and May, just before the rainy season. It therefore needs to be stored for several months until September, which is the best sowing time except at the extremes of its altitudinal range. In nurseries above 2000 m on cold sites, sowing shortly after collection (before the monsoon) may be necessary for planting out in the following monsoon, say 14 months later. If the seeds (correctly called stones) need to be stored over the monsoon, ambient conditions will be warm and humid, and great care must be taken to get them processed and properly dried as soon as possible. If this is not done, the onset of the monsoon will make drying difficult. The stones should be dried on trays for at least 2-3 days in the sun to obtain a sufficiently low moisture content. Care should also be taken to keep them cool after drying. If longer storage is needed, then they should be sent to the NTSP for cold storage.

Alnus nepalensis: Since this species matures during the winter, it can be sown shortly after collection and planted out after 5-6 months in nurseries on favourable sites up to 1500 m. However, in many nurseries at higher altitudes or on cold sites, the best time to sow is in August and September towards the end of the monsoon. At the upper end of the species' altitudinal range, in nurseries above 2000 m and especially in those on unfavourable sites, the seed should be sown in April or May. In both these cases, seed storage will be necessary, and it will be essential to have the seed dried as much as possible, and also kept as cool as possible. Alnus seed will quickly reabsorb moisture after drying, so that it must be put very quickly into sealed bags (within an hour of being dried, and certainly not left exposed overnight). As with Prunus, 2-3 days in the sun should be sufficient for drying.

Pinus roxburghii: Since this species matures from January to March, just after the winter months, it is often too late to sow it immediately, except in nurseries below 1500 m. At higher

Seed storage in the nursery: polythene and cloth bags in ventilated metal trunk

altitudes and in nurseries on cold sites, the best sowing time is in September, so that the seed will have to be stored for 6 months. To allow for the poor seed years that occur with this species, storage for one or more years will be necessary. However, its apparent hardiness in storage indicates that, provided adequate measures are taken, decline of viability will not be a problem. Storage for 2 years or more should be in the NTSP cold store.

Pinus wallichiana: This species matures from October to November, just before the winter months, and should not be sown immediately, but must be stored until April. This is the best sowing time for nurseries up to 2500 m, from which the seedlings will be planted out after 15 months. Provided care is taken to dry and store the seed as recommended, it can be stored in the nursery for up to 6-9 months.

For longer periods, it should be sent to the NTSP for cold storage.

In conclusion, the recommended practice for all orthodox seed stored in the nursery or district offices is to dry it immediately on raised trays with wire-mesh bottoms, or failing that on a nanglo supported by three stones, for 2-3 days in the sun, and then pack it immediately into a thick polythene bag, squeeze out the air, and tie tightly with string. Put the bag in a can or metal trunk, and store just off the floor in the coolest part of the store. For further details, see the NTSP/CFDP seed handling manual.

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References

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Willan, R.L. (1985). A guide to forest seed handling, with special reference to the tropics. FAO Forestry Paper 20/2.

Keywords: Prunus cerasoides; Alnus nepalensis; Pinus roxburghii; Pinus wallichiana; seed storage.

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Appendix

Notes on FRP Storage Experiment NUR 85/19

1. The table and graphs give the mean results of each test. Individual replicate results are not shown.

2. All tests were carried out following ISTA rules as far as possible. Each germination test consisted of 4 replicates of 50 seeds each (or 0.25 g for Alnus), sown in sterile sand within closed boxes. When possible, a regime of 12 h/20°C/dark:12 h/30°C/light was used, otherwise 25°C constant. Each moisture content test consisted of 2 replicates, dried to constant weight at 105°C, and the result expressed on a wet weight basis.

3. The refrigerator temperature was approx. 4-5°C constant. Ambient conditions in the Chalnakhel nursery shed can be gauged from average climatic data in Kathmandu valley (1324 m, 27° 44'N, 85° 20'E):

	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
Mean rainfall, mm	18	24	26	52	96	227	369	335	159	46	8	4
Mean temp., °C	9.5	11.9	15.6	19.3	22.0	23.6	23.8	23.6	22.5	19.5	14.6	10.8

(Mean annual rainfall 1364 mm).

4. Months of testing can be related to climate as follows:

Initial	3 months	6 months	9 months	12 months	15 months	18 months
June 85	Sept. 85	Dec. 85	March 86	June 86	Sept. 86	Dec. 86

5. For the purposes of the experiment, the metal trunk was ventilated with 5-mm holes so that seed stored in cloth bags would be aerated.

6. The experiment will continue for at least another 6 months, and it is planned to continue with the nursery storage methods of Pinus until all viability is lost. A similar experiment is being conducted with Dalbergia sissoo.

Graphs (— = Method 1: refrigerator, glass jar. - - - = Method 2:

Prunus cerasoides

germination

moisture content

Alnus nepalensis

germination

moisture content

nursery, polythene bag. = Method 3: nursery, cloth bag)

Pinus roxburghii

Pinus wallichiana

Tables

Prunus cerasoides

Percentage germination						Percentage moisture content						
Time (months)						Time (months)						
0	3	6	9	12	15	0	3	6	9	12	15	
						Method						
74	89	94	93	97	85	(1) Refrigerator	9.5	9.9	8.7	10.1	10.0	10.3
74	93	91	90	63	0	(2) Polythene bag	9.5	10.3	9.7	10.5	10.5	10.8
74	1	0	not tested			(3) Cloth bag	9.5	12.4	12.2	not tested		

Alnus nepalensis

Viable seeds per gram						Percentage moisture content						
Time (months)						Time (months)						
0	3	6	9	12	15	0	3	6	9	12	15	
						Method						
616	742	725*	708	722	615	(1) Refrig.	10.4	9.6	10.1	10.9	10.5	10.2
616	542	455	305	149	0	(2) Poly. bag	10.4	9.5	9.4	10.3	10.4	10.6
616	0	0	not tested			(3) Cloth bag	10.4	11.2	11.8	not tested		

Pinus roxburghii

Percentage germination						Percentage moisture content						
Time (months)						Time (months)						
0	3	6	9	12	15	0	3	6	9	12	15	
						Method						
93	91*	89	87	91	92	(1) Refrigerator	8.0	8.3*	8.6	7.9	8.0	8.1
93	92*	91	90	84	75	(2) Polythene bag	8.0	8.6*	9.2	8.2	8.2	8.6
93	95*	97	88	91	80	(3) Cloth bag	8.0	8.8*	9.6*	10.4	9.5	11.2

Pinus wallichiana

Percentage germination						Percentage moisture content						
Time (months)						Time (months)						
0	3	6	9	12	15	0	3	6	9	12	15	
						Method						
54	64*	73	53	59	60	(1) Refrigerator	9.9	9.4	10.0	10.2	10.2	9.8
54	61*	67	79	62	29	(2) Polythene bag	9.9	9.4	9.9	10.2	10.2	10.5
54	50*	47	30	18	0	(3) Cloth bag	9.9	11.5	12.0	11.5	10.5	12.4

*Test not valid, therefore estimated as mean of previous and following tests.